

Synthesis and Comparative Study of Energy Parameters Calculated from d-d Transitions of Some Cobalt(II) Complexes

SUDHINDRA N. MISRA*, R. K. JAIN and G. K. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

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Complexes of cobalt(II) hexafluorosilicate and hexafluorotitanate with thiourea and substituted thioureas have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis and electronic spectral studies. The various ligand field parameters have been calculated and used to explain the stereochemistry of cobalt(II) in these complexes. The magnetic moments of these complexes (4.8-5.30 B.M.) indicate that all of them are spin free with three unpaired electrons.

THE absorption spectra of cobalt(II) ions in different lattice sites have been the subject of several investigations¹⁻⁴. Co(II) being a d⁷ ion has a special affinity for tetrahedral structure. However, the complexes studied in the present work are all hexacoordinated. A number of complexes of cobalt have been reported over the last two years, both with low spin⁵ and high spin configuration. It was therefore considered of interest to investigate reactions of fluorotitanate and fluorosilicate of Co(II) with neutral ambivalent ligand like thiourea.

The hexafluorosilicates or hexafluorotitanates of cobalt, [Co(H₂O)₆].SiF₆, [Co(H₂O)₆].TiF₆ undergo reactions of the type :

These complexes dissolve freely in alcohol and have been characterized by elemental analysis, spectral and magnetic studies.

Results and Discussion

Cobalt(II) ion is a d⁷ ion and has a special affinity for tetrahedral coordination but the complexes described in the present study are hexacoordinated. Thiourea is an ambivalent ligand and can coordinate to metal ion either through nitrogen or sulphur⁵⁻⁸. Cobalt(II) itself is a border line metal ion and thus shows equal affinity for hard and soft ligands.

The addition of thiourea or substituted thiourea to an ethanolic solution of [Co(H₂O)₆].SiF₆ or [Co(H₂O)₆].TiF₆ leads to the isolation of sparingly soluble species where four thiourea molecules enter the inner sphere of coordination while fluorosilicate or fluorotitanate group is retained in the outer sphere of coordination.

The infrared spectral studies of these derivatives have indicated that the thiourea molecule is linked to metal via sulphur thus yielding the chromophore

CoD₂S₄. The complexes are pinkish red in colour. They appear to lose water on heating beyond 220° and acquire pinkish colour. The complexes obtained after heating become insoluble in alcohol and do not melt up to 280° but undergo decomposition. Analysis and magnetic moment values (Guoy method at 300 ± 1K) are recorded in Table 1. The electronic spectral data are given in Tables 2 and 3.

In the weak field, the experimentally observed spin allowed transitions in cobalt(II) are in the order of increasing energy via ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ¹T_{2g}(ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P)(ν₃). The ν₃ band, which determines the magnitude of 10Dq occurs at 19300-24000 cm⁻¹ and this assignment is based on similar band at 20000 cm⁻¹ in hexaquo cobalt(II) ion. The weak band occurring in the vicinity of 16000-18000 cm⁻¹ is a broad band. The pattern of absorption spectra of these complexes is identical with that of hexaquo cobalt(II) ion suggesting that the stereochemistry of metal ion of the two types of species are almost identical. Slight distortion from the idealized octahedral stereochemistry can be visualized in view of the non-identical nature of the coordinating atoms in chromophore CoN₄O₂. This finds support from the existence of two bands in the region 15000-20000 cm⁻¹ to which is generally attributed the splitting of the band⁹. The values of Racah parameter B calculated⁵ following weak field coupling lie in the range 674-696 cm⁻¹ in different complexes as compared to 972 cm⁻¹ for hexaquo cobalt(II) ion.

Naturally the low value of B for the complex is less than that for Co²⁺ free ion and thus the magnitude of nephelauxetic ratio, β, will be less than unity. The value of nephelauxetic effect (1 - β) is quite high in hexaquo cobalt(II) ion (0.933) which is quite understandable but as the water molecules are slowly substituted by thiourea ligand the nephelauxetic effect increases, thereby increasing the magnitude of covalent contribution. The values of 10Dq for these mixed ligand complexes are in the range of 7665 to

* For correspondence.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COBALT FLUOROSILICATE AND FLUOROTITANATE COMPLEXES

Complex	Mol. wt.	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)			Magnetic moment B.M.
		Cobalt	Sulphur	Nitrogen	
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{CS})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{SiF}_6$	541.504	10.78 (10.88)	23.59 (23.68)	20.61 (20.69)	4.80
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{CS})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{TlF}_6$	561.318	10.35 (10.49)	23.78 (23.84)	19.85 (19.96)	4.92
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{C}_2\text{S})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{SiF}_6$	701.7624	8.92 (8.99)	18.13 (18.27)	15.87 (15.96)	4.97
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{C}_2\text{S})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{TlF}_6$	721.5764	8.04 (8.16)	17.68 (17.77)	15.44 (15.53)	5.04
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{C}_7\text{S})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{SiF}_6$	893.9384	6.47 (6.59)	14.29 (14.34)	12.99 (12.53)	5.10
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{C}_7\text{S})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{TlF}_6$	913.7524	6.38 (6.45)	13.88 (14.03)	12.11 (12.26)	5.20
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_{11}\text{C}_{11}\text{S})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{SiF}_6$	729.6928	7.95 (8.07)	8.64 (8.78)	7.59 (7.67)	5.18
$[\text{Co}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_{11}\text{C}_{11}\text{S})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{TlF}_6$	749.5068	7.74 (7.86)	8.43 (8.55)	7.31 (7.47)	5.32

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR SOME CO(II) COMPLEXES

Co(II) complexes	ν_1 (cm ⁻¹)	ν_2 (cm ⁻¹)	ν_3 (cm ⁻¹)	ν_3/ν_1	ν_3/ν_2
$\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$	83333	17857	20833	2.50	1.16
Co-HFT-ATU	8438.5	16260	19305	2.29	1.20
Co-HFT-TU	8474.5	16393	19417	2.27	1.18
Co-HFT-PTU	8438.5	16260	19417	2.28	1.19
Co-HFT-DPTU	8438.5	16260	19607	2.29	1.18
Co-HFS-ATU	8474.5	16129	19417	2.29	1.17
Co-HFS-TU	8438.8	16260	19417	2.30	1.19
Co-HFS-PTU	8474.5	16260	19607	2.31	1.20
Co-HFS-DPTU	8474.5	16260	19678	2.32	1.21

HFT=hexafluorotitanate; HFS=hexafluorosilicate; ATU=allyl thiourea; TU=thiourea; PTU=phenyl thiourea and DPTU=diphenyl thiourea.

7856 cm⁻¹ and the ν_3/ν_1 ratio is ~ 2.30 . These suggest that the complexes described in this study are of the same type of stereochemistry. In our earlier study of Co(II) complexes of dimethylglyoxime and thiourea, the isolated complexes were spin paired with very low magnitude of Racah parameter B. The complexes had sufficient covalent character as the nephelauxetic effect magnitude was much higher than the complexes reported in the present study. This is quite understandable since the complexes as studied in this article are of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{Tu})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot\text{SiF}_6$ or TlF_6 , where the inner sphere of coordination is occupied by all the six

neutral ligands to give chromophore of the CoN_4O_2 type while the complexes described in the earlier study were of the chromophore CoN_4S_2 type. The four nitrogen coordinating sites of the later series complexes was provided by dimethylglyoxime ligands while the thiourea molecules were coordinated through sulphur sites.

The thiourea molecules were arranged octahedrally in *cis* position. The complexes obtained in

this study are formed by gradual replacement of (up to four) thiourea molecules while the two water molecules are still intact. This will naturally cause less covalency in the metal ligand bond. The less covalent contribution is also expected when the highly ionic fluorosilicate or fluorotitanate anion is attached to the outer sphere of coordination. These two factors enhance some ionic contribution with the result that the magnitude of $1-\beta$ in these complexes is not high as compared to thiourea adducts of cobalt dimethylglyoxime complexes⁴.

The magnetic moments of these complexes suggest that these are all spin free cobalt(II) com-

TABLE 3—COMPUTED VALUES OF VARIOUS PARAMETERS FOR SOME CO(II) COMPLEXES

Co(II) complexes	B (cm ⁻¹)	C (cm ⁻¹)	D (cm ⁻¹)	E C.F.A.E (cm ⁻¹)	10Dq (cm ⁻¹)	F ₂ (cm ⁻¹)	F ₄ (cm ⁻¹)	F [*] (cm ⁻¹)	F ⁴ (cm ⁻¹)	β	h_x	P
$\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$	912.7	4226	7606	7619	9524	1516.2	120.7	69568.40	53247.6	0.933	0.279	1.020
Co-HFT-ATU	674.8	3125	4614	6124	7655	1121.1	89.28	54940.19	39375.0	0.689	1.296	0.820
Co-HFT-TU	678.2	3140	5642	6258	7822	1126.7	89.7	55211.79	39564.0	0.693	1.279	0.838
Co-HFT-PTU	689.9	3194	5749	6257	7821	1146.4	91.3	56163.09	40244.4	0.705	1.229	0.838
Co-HFT-DPTU	710.3	3289	5909	6285	7856	1180.1	93.97	57827.69	41441.4	0.726	1.142	0.842
Co-HFS-ATU	674.9	3125	5614	6124	7655	1121.3	89.28	54945.09	39375.0	0.690	1.292	0.820
Co-HFS-TU	689.9	3194	5749	6257	7821	1146.15	91.25	56163.09	40244.4	0.705	1.229	0.838
Co-HFS-PTU	696.0	3223	5790	6228	7785	1156.4	92.08	5664.99	40609.8	0.712	1.200	0.834
Co-HFS-DPTU	696.2	3224	5792	6228	7785	1156.7	92.1	56681.79	40622.4	0.712	1.200	0.834

Abbreviations are the same as in Table 2.

plexes with magnetic moment in the range of 4.80 to 5.30 B.M. indicating the presence of three unpaired electrons. The spin free configuration of these complexes are expected in view of the presence of higher negative fluorine in the complex. Though it is present in the outer sphere of coordination yet its effect is reflected in the physical properties of the complexes. The complexes are sufficiently soluble in polar organic solvents.

The covalency in the metal-ligand bond originates in the change in the inter-electronic repulsion parameters which are interpreted in terms of Racah (B, C) or Slater-Condon (F_2, F_4) or Slater-Condon Shortley (F^2, F^4) parameters which are interrelated¹⁰.

The nephelauxetic effect is a result of two factors viz. nephelauxetic parameter for the ligand (h_x) and for metal ion (K_m): $h_x \times K_m = 1 - \beta$. The value of K_m for Co^{2+} was used to compute the nephelauxetic contribution of the ligands.

It has been observed that a similar trend of covalent bonding is followed in both titanate and silicate complex (order of B in the series is ATU < TU < PTU < DPTU).

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